

INVESTIGATION OF EFFECT OF INLET DISTORTION ON FLUTTER STABILITY OF A TRANSONIC FAN USING AN APPROXIMATE TIME DOMAIN NONLINEAR HARMONIC METHOD

Hangkong Wu

School of Mechanical Engineering
Xi'an Jiaotong University
Shaanxi, 710048, China

Haideng Zhang*

National Key Lab of Aerospace Power
System and Plasma Technology
Air Force Engineering University
Shaanxi, 710082, China

*Correspondence: zhanghaideng@126.com

Yun Wu

National Key Lab of Aerospace Power
System and Plasma Technology
Air Force Engineering University
Shaanxi, 710082, China

Dingxi Wang

School of Power and Energy
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Shaanxi, 710129, China

ABSTRACT

Inlet distortion, arising from factors such as boundary layer ingestion (BLI) and inlet struts, is found to have a significant impact on both aerodynamic and aeroelastic performance of aero-engines. The current whole-annulus unsteady time domain method, used to evaluate its effect on flutter stability and/or forced response, is too time-consuming to be practical even with high-performance computers available, thus limiting its broader engineering applications. Additionally, when the unsteady frequency of inlet distortion is close to the blade vibration frequency, the harmonic balance (HB) method suffers from solution instability due to the large condition number of the discrete Fourier transform matrix. To address the aforementioned issues, this work employs an approximate time-domain nonlinear harmonic method (ATDNHM), which simplifies the discrete Fourier transform matrix by omitting the coupled terms. Compared to the time domain method, the ATDNHM, when combined with the phase shift boundary condition method, can significantly reduce computational cost. More importantly, the ATDNHM is capable of reducing the condition number of the discrete Fourier transform matrix, which leads to a more stable solution com-

pared to the HB method. To demonstrate the advantages of the ATDNHM, a transonic fan subjected to inlet distortion caused by the wing is considered. The results for the distorted inlet case are compared with those for a uniform inlet. The unsteady pressure and worksum density on the blade surfaces are extracted and carefully analyzed to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms.

Keywords: inlet distortion; aeroelastic; approximate time-domain nonlinear harmonic method; harmonic balance; fan

NOMENCLATURE

E_1, E_2 discrete Fourier transform matrix

E_1^{-1}, E_2^{-1} inverse matrix of E_1 and E_2

f unsteady frequency (Hz)

F_1, F_2 time spectral source term operator

F, G, H convective flux vectors

N_1, N_2, N_h the number of harmonics

$N_{1,t}, N_{2,t}$ the number of time instants

R spatial residual vector

S source term vector

- t physical time (s)
- U conservative flow variable vector
- U^* Fourier coefficients of U
- U^A, U^B imaginary and real parts of Fourier coefficients
- $v_{g,x}, v_{g,\theta}, v_{g,r}$ grid moving velocities (m/s)
- V_x, V_θ, V_r Viscous flux vectors
- x, r, θ cylindrical coordinate system
- ω angular frequency of unsteadiness (rad/s)
- κ condition number

1 INTRODUCTION

Inlet distortion, arising from factors such as boundary layer ingestion (BLI) and inlet struts, can significantly impact both aerodynamic and aeroelastic performance of compressors/fans such as stall margin and flutter stability. Figure. 1 presents the inlet total pressure distortion caused by the wing. In the past two decades, considerable effort has been dedicated to studying the effect of inlet distortion on the aeroelastic performance of turbomachinery blades.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of the configuration (a); and the total pressure at the inlet (b).

Inlet distortion can cause unsteady loading on the blade surfaces of compressors/fans, leading to low engine order forced response, which in turn affects the high-cycle fatigue life of the blades. Pan et al. [1] employed the transonic compressor rotor,

NASA Rotor 67 [2], to study the effect of inlet distortion extent on the forced response. The results indicated that the second-order excitation frequency from the inlet distortion was close to the vibration frequency of the first bending mode, resulting in a low engine order forced response. Furthermore, as the inlet distortion angle increased, the modal forcing initially showed an upward trend but started to reduce at 90° . Latter, the same test case was employed by Pan et al. [3] to study the effect of intensity of the inlet distortion on forced response. The results showed that the modal forcing increased with the intensity of the distortion. Specifically, when the intensity of the distortion increased from 0.05 to 0.10, the modal forcing increased by one order of magnitude.

Additionally, inlet distortion has an effect on the time-averaged flow field, which in turn influences the flutter performance of blades. Yan et al. [4] developed a fast calculation method to obtain the aerodynamic damping at different nodal diameters (ND) under the distorted inlet condition. The results showed that the aerodynamic damping of different circumferential blades was different. Their values were closely in line with the distorted region. Chen et al. [5] also observed that the aerodynamic damping of different blades did not remain constant around the circumference, but instead varied periodically. This behavior arises because the computation of the aerodynamic damping takes into account the work induced by the inlet distortion [6]. When this distorted work has a destabilizing effect on a blade, it reduces the aerodynamic damping.

The common feature of the above work is that the whole-annulus time domain method is adopted to perform fluid-structure interaction (FSI) analysis, requiring a large amount of computing resources. To reduce computational cost, Li et al. [7] combined the time domain method with a phase-lag approach [8], reducing the computational domain from the whole annulus to a single-passage one. The results showed that the circumferential wavelength of the inlet distortion had a huge impact on the time-averaged flow field. Longer wavelength resulted in a more pronounced unsteadiness in the flow, which notably impacted the flutter performance. In terms of computational cost, the single-passage time domain method could reduce it by a factor of twenty compared to a whole-annulus one. However, this method required additional iterations to filter the initial conditions, which could reduce computational efficiency in certain cases.

Currently, the frequency domain methods, which adopt a truncated Fourier series to approximate flow variables, are widely employed for aeroelastic analysis. These methods offer a significant advantage over the time domain approaches due to their lower computational cost, making them more favorable for engineering applications. However, the harmonic balance method (HB) [9], one type of the frequency domain methods, can encounter solution instability, especially when the excitation frequency is near the blade vibration frequency. This issue arises because the condition number of the discrete Fourier

transform matrix becomes too large, preventing convergence of the solution [10]. The approximate time-domain nonlinear harmonic method (ATDNHM) proposed by Wang et al. [11] simplifies the discrete Fourier transform matrix by omitting the coupled terms. Numerical tests indicate that the condition number of the approximate discrete Fourier transform matrix remains relatively stable even as the unsteady flow fields change, leading to a more stable solution compared to the HB method. Building on its advantages, the ATDNHM is utilized in this work to conduct flutter analysis under distorted inlet conditions. The mechanism of flutter instability induced by inlet distortion will be thoroughly investigated.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the flow governing equations and the corresponding numerical methods adopted in this work; Section 3 provides an overview of the test case and the numerical settings used in the flow field analysis; Section 4 introduces the decoupled flutter analysis system adopted in this work; Section 5 offers a detailed analysis of the unsteady flow fields and explores the mechanism of flutter instability induced by inlet distortion; Section 6 summarizes the findings and draws conclusions based on the flow field analysis.

2 METHODOLOGY

The three-dimensional Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equation in a cylindrical coordinate system can be expressed by

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(F - Uv_{g,x} - V_x)}{\partial x} + \frac{(\partial G - Uv_{g,\theta} - V_\theta)}{r\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial r(H - Uv_{g,r} - V_r)}{r\partial r} = S \quad (1)$$

The detailed expressions for each term in the equation above can be found in the reference [12].

To simplify the following derivation, the equation above can be written in the following semi-discrete form

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + R(U) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where R is the lumped spatial residual vector.

For a flutter case with inlet distortion, the flow variables can be decomposed into three components: the time-averaged part, the perturbation part due to blade vibration U_1' and inlet distortion U_2' .

$$U = \bar{U} + U_1' + U_2' \quad (3)$$

Since the unsteady frequencies of unsteadiness can be known *a priori*, a truncated Fourier series can be employed to approximate the unsteady disturbances

$$U_l' = \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} [U_{i,l}^A \sin(\omega_{l,i}t) + U_{i,l}^B \cos(\omega_{l,i}t)] \quad (l = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

where N_l ($l = 1, 2$) represents the number of harmonics retained for the analysis of U_l' ($l = 1, 2$), and $\omega_{l,1}$ ($l = 1, 2$) denotes the fundamental angular frequency of unsteadiness associated with U_l' ($l = 1, 2$). For instance, $\omega_{l,1}$ ($l = 1, 2$) corresponds to the blade vibration frequency, which can be determined through a modal analysis in advance.

2.1 HB METHOD

In Eqs. 3 and 4, there are $2 \times (N_1 + N_2) + 1$ unknowns, and thus $2 \times (N_1 + N_2) + 1$ equations are required to obtain a determined system. The HB method first selects $2 \times (N_1 + N_2) + 1$ time instants at the time axis, after which the time-domain flow variables at these selected time instants are obtained by solving the HB governing equation system. Finally, the discrete Fourier transform method is applied to convert the flow variables from the time domain to the frequency domain. For cases with at least two fundamental frequencies, the almost period Fourier transform method tends to be adopted to determine non-uniform time instants. The interested readers can refer to reference [13] for the detailed algorithm.

Rewrite Eqs.3 and 4 into the following matrix form

$$U = E_1 U^* = [I \ T_1 \ T_2] \begin{bmatrix} \bar{U} \\ U_1' \\ U_2' \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where I is a column vector with a dimension of N_t ($= 2 \times (N_1 + N_2) + 1$). All their elements have the value of 1. T_1 and T_2 are defined by

$$T_l = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\omega_{l,1}t_1) & \cos(\omega_{l,1}t_1) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l}t_1) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l}t_1) \\ \sin(\omega_{l,1}t_2) & \cos(\omega_{l,1}t_2) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l}t_2) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l}t_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sin(\omega_{l,1}t_{N_t}) & \cos(\omega_{l,1}t_{N_t}) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l}t_{N_t}) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l}t_{N_t}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

According to Eq. 5, the time derivative of the flow variables can be calculated by

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} U^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial T_2}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} U^* = E_t E_1^{-1} U = F_1 U \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eq. 7 into Eq. 2 yields the flow governing equation in a HB form

$$F_1 U + R(U) = 0 \quad (8)$$

2.2 APPROXIMATE TIME-DOMAIN NONLINEAR HARMONIC METHOD

When the blade vibration frequency is close to the excitation frequency induced by inlet distortion, the condition number of the discrete Fourier transform matrix (E_1) in Eq. 5 will be too large to obtain a converged solution.

Unlike the HB method, the ATDNHM simplifies the discrete Fourier transform matrix by excluding the coupling terms. Therefore, Eq. 5 can be rewritten in the following matrix form

$$U = E_2 U^* = \begin{bmatrix} I_1 & T_{11} & 0 \\ I_2 & 0 & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{U} \\ U'_1 \\ U'_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $I_l (l = 1, 2)$ with a dimension of $2 \times N_l + 1 (l = 1, 2)$. All their elements have the value of 1. 0 is a zero matrix. T_{11} and T_{22} are defined by

$$T_{ll} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,1}) & \cos(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,1}) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,1}) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,1}) \\ \sin(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,2}) & \cos(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,2}) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,2}) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,2}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sin(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,N_{l,t}}) & \cos(\omega_{l,1} t_{l,N_{l,t}}) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,N_{l,t}}) & \cos(\omega_{l,N_l} t_{l,N_{l,t}}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where $N_{l,t} = 2 \times N_l + 1$.

Compared to the HB method, the time instants will be uniformly distributed over the temporal period of each unsteady disturbance for the ATDNHM, leading to the following equation for the calculation of time instants

$$t_{l,i} = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_{l,1} \cdot N_{l,t}} \cdot i (i = 0, 1, \dots, 2N_l) \quad (11)$$

It can be seen from Eq. 9 that there are $2 \times (N_1 + N_2) + 2$ equations, which exceed the number of unknowns, leading to an overdetermined system. It is impossible to invert the matrix E_2 . To address this issue, a pseudo-inverse matrix is introduced

$$E_2^{-1} = (E_2^T E_2)^{-1} E_2^T \quad (12)$$

Based on Eq. 9, the time derivatives of the flow variables can be expressed by

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial t} U^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial T_{11}}{\partial t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial T_{22}}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} E_2^{-1} U = F_2 U \quad (13)$$

Substitute Eq. 13 into Eq. 2, and we have

$$F_2 U + R(U) = 0 \quad (14)$$

2.3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

To demonstrate the advantage of the ATDNHM over the HB method in terms of solution stability, an unsteady disturbance is given by

$$w = u_1 \cdot \sin(2\pi f_1 t) + u_2 \cdot \cos(2\pi f_2 t) \quad (15)$$

where u_1 and u_2 are both set to 0.1; f_1 and f_2 are set to 100 Hz and 110 Hz, respectively. Four harmonics are retained to analyze the unsteady disturbance: the first two harmonics correspond to u_1 , while the remaining two correspond to u_2 .

First, the time instants are computed, as they are needed to compute the discrete Fourier matrix. For the HB method, the APFT method is used to determine the non-uniform time instants, as shown in Fig. 2(a). For the ATDNHM, two sets of uniform time instants are calculated using Eq.11, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

Next, the condition numbers (see Eq. 16) of the discrete Fourier transform matrix E_1 from the HB method and E_2 from the ATDNHM are calculated.

$$\kappa(E_l) = \|E_l\| \cdot \|E_l^{-1}\| (l = 1, 2) \quad (16)$$

The results indicate that the condition number of the HB method is approximately 3.07, while for the ATDNHM, it is 2.00. A smaller condition number indicates a more stable solution [14, 15].

3 TEST CASES

The test case studied here is a transonic fan with an inlet strut (also referred to as the wing), as shown in Fig. 1(a). The detailed design parameters of the fan are as follows: thirty-one blades, a tip gap of 2.703 mm, a design rotational speed of 10098 revolutions per minute.

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) present the computational meshes used in the subsequent numerical analyses. The number of grid points for the inlet strut is around 5.7 million, while for the

(a) HB

(b) ATDNHM

FIGURE 2. Distributions of time instants for the HB method (a); and for the ATDNHM (b).

single-passage computational domain of the fan, it is approximately 1.2 million.

In the numerical analysis, the boundary conditions for the inlet of the strut are specified as follows: a total pressure of 101325 Pa, a total temperature of 288.15 K, a yaw angle of 0 degrees, and a pitch angle of 0 degrees. At the outlet, the area-averaged back pressure of 60795 Pa is specified and the radial equilibrium formula is used to determine its radial profile.

Figure 1(b) presents the total pressure at the fan inlet. Due to the effect of the wing's boundary layer, two distorted regions are identified where the total pressure is lower than that in the main flow region. The relative difference in total pressure between the distorted and clean regions is about 5%.

Figures 4 presents the Mach number contours of the fan at three different spans: 10%, 50% and 95%. Flow separations on the suction surface can be clearly observed especially above the middle span, indicating that the operating point is close to the stall boundary. At this operating point, the calculated steady-state aerodynamic performance of the fan is characterized by a mass flow rate of 105 kg/s, a total pressure ratio of 1.6158, and an isentropic efficiency of 75.44%. In the subsequent part, flutter

(a) inlet strut

blade-to-blade view

meridional view

(b) fan

FIGURE 3. Computational meshes for the inlet strut (a); and for the fan (b).

analysis will be conducted at this operating point.

4 DECOUPLED FLUTTER ANALYSIS SYSTEM

For turbomachinery blades, where the mass ratio is typically larger than 100, the effect of its surrounding flows on blades' mode shape and vibration frequency is negligible and can be omitted. Therefore, a completely decoupled fluid-structure analysis system [16], as shown in Fig. 5, can be adopted to perform efficient and simultaneously accurate flutter analysis. Four main steps are required:

1. Modal analysis is to acquire the mode shape and vibration

FIGURE 4. Mach number contours of the fan at three different spans.

frequency of a blade. This step is conducted using the commercial software-ANSYS;

2. Mode shape interpolation involves transferring the mode shape from a finite-element mesh to a flow mesh. This step is accomplished using the radial basis function, which effectively maps the mode shape onto the flow mesh;
3. Mesh perturbation involves updating mesh at each time step to account for the blade's dynamic deformation. In this work, the mesh is perturbed using the linear elastic method, which effectively preserves mesh quality, especially for cases with small displacements;
4. Flutter analysis is performed using the moving grid technique, with the unsteady flow fields being analyzed using the ATDNHM.

FIGURE 5. Fully decoupled flutter analysis system.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 MODAL ANALYSIS

The fan blade is made of titanium alloy, with a Poisson's ratio of 0.3, a density of 4500 kg/m^3 and an elastic modulus of 120 GPa. Additionally, the fan blade is designed with a tenon connection structure, leading to a negligible effect of the disk on the blades' vibration properties. In the modal analysis, only the fan blade is considered, with the blade root being fixed, as shown in Fig. 6(a). The hexahedron mesh is adopted and the total number of grid nodes is approximately 30,000. Figures 6(b) present the mode shapes of the first three modes. In these figures, 1F denotes the first flapping mode, 1T represents the first torsion mode, and 2F is the second flapping mode. The corresponding blade vibration frequencies of each mode are 253.83 Hz, 552.12 Hz and 620.52 Hz, respectively.

FIGURE 6. The finite-element mesh (a); and the first three mode shapes (b).

5.2 FFT ANALYSIS

To save computational cost, only the fan is considered in the flutter analysis. To account for the effect of inlet distortion on flutter stability, the total pressure extracted from the whole configuration, as shown in Fig. 1(b), is used as the inlet boundary condition. Since the ATDNHM, combined with the phase shift boundary condition, employs a single-passage computational domain, a fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis is performed on the circumferential distribution of the total pressure at different

radial locations to reconstruct the solution. In this work, five different locations are selected including 10% (marked as 1), 30% (marked as 2), 50% (marked as 3), 70% (marked as 4) and 90% (marked as 5), as shown in Fig. 7(a). It can be seen in Fig. 7(b) that to retain over 99% of flow field information, at least fifteen spatial harmonics are required to reconstruct the circumferential non-uniformity. Figure 8 compares the original and reconstructed total pressure at the inlet. In the legend, N denotes the number of harmonics. As the number of harmonics increases, the agreement between the original and reconstructed total pressure improves. No visible difference in total pressure is observed between fifteen and twenty harmonics. To balance solution accuracy with computational cost, fifteen spatial harmonics will be retained to analyze circumferential inlet distortion at 50% span. The reconstructed results are cross-verified with the FFT analysis results. Similar conclusions hold for other radial locations; for brevity, these are not repeated here.

(a) radial locations

(b) FFT results

FIGURE 7. Radial locations selected for a FFT analysis (a); and the FFT analysis results at 50% span (b).

FIGURE 8. Comparison of the original and reconstructed total pressure at the inlet.

5.3 FLUTTER ANALYSES

First, the flutter analysis under a uniform inlet condition is performed. At the inlet, the area-averaged total pressure of 99855 Pa computed from Fig.1(b) is specified. The traveling wave method (TWM) [17] is used to compute the logarithmic decay (log-dec) against inter blade phase angles (IBPA). Figure 9 compares the log-dec value obtained from the in-house flow solver TurboXDM with those from the commercial software CFX. The overall trend of the log-decs obtained from the two solvers are consistent. Although a visible difference in the log-dec value at an IBPA of -23.23° can be observed, the log-decs from both solvers remain negative, indicating an unstable aeroelastic system. The above results verify the high accuracy of flutter performance predictions using the in-house flow solver.

FIGURE 9. Comparison of the log-dec for the first mode between TurboXDM and CFX.

Figure 10 presents the log-decs against IBPAs for the second and third modes. Compared to the log-decs of the first mode, as shown in Fig. 9, the log-decs of the other two modes are significantly higher than zero. This indicates no predicted flutter instability for these two modes. The subsequent flutter analyses will solely focus on the first mode.

FIGURE 10. Log-decs against IBPAs for the second and third modes obtained from TurboXDM.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of log-decs under the uniform and distorted inlet conditions.

Second, the log-decs computed under both uniform and distorted inlet conditions are compared, as shown in Fig. 11. When

the IBPAs range from $[-46.46^\circ -11.61^\circ]$, the effect of inlet distortion on the log-decs exhibits an upward trend but the sign remains unchanged, leading to consistent assessment of flutter stability. However at an IBPA of 0° , the log-dec value computed under the uniform inlet condition is positive, indicating a stable flutter system. In contrast, under the distorted inlet condition, the log-dec value becomes negative, leading to an unstable flutter system.

FIGURE 12. Distributions of area-averaged worksum on blade surfaces under the uniform inlet condition (a); and the distorted inlet condition (b).

Figures 12(a) and 12(b) present the distributions of area-averaged worksum at an IBPA of 0° on blade surfaces under the uniform and distorted inlet conditions, respectively. Figure 13 compares the worksum across the whole span. In these figures, L.E. and T.E. denote the leading and trailing edges, and P.S. and S.S. represent the pressure and surface sides, respectively. On the P.S., the worksum is positive across the entire span, whereas on the S.S. it is negative, indicating that flutter instability predominately originates from the P.S.. On the S.S., under the distorted inlet condition, the negative worksum further decreases from 50% span to 70% span. This is due to the expansion of

the negative worksum region from the leading edge to the shock wave. From 70% to 80% span and 30% to 50% span on the S.S., positive worksum appears at the leading edge under the distorted inlet condition, leading to a slight increase in the overall worksum in these regions compared to the uniform inlet condition. Overall, the worksum on the S.S. exhibits a downward trend. On the P.S., the positive worksum increases significantly from 40% to 75% span and also near the blade tip, while it slightly decreases from 75% to 85% span. The increase in worksum from 40% to 75% span is attributed to the intensified positive worksum region around the shock wave. This increase in positive worksum leads to a more unstable flutter system. The decrease in worksum from 75% to 85% span is due to the expansion of the negative worksum region at the leading edge. These results suggest that inlet distortion increases the worksum on the P.S. while slightly decreasing the worksum on the S.S..

FIGURE 14. Comparison of worksum along the streamline at 98% span.

FIGURE 13. Comparison of worksum along the whole span.

Figure 14 makes a comparison in the worksum along the streamline at 98% span. A visible difference in the area-averaged worksum is observed on the S.S.. The positive area-averaged worksum at the shock wave suggests that the shock wave has a destabilizing effect on flutter. After the shock wave, where the flow separation region is located, the worksum approaches zero, indicating that the flow separation almost has no effect on flutter stability at the blade tip. Compared to the uniform inlet condition, flutter analyses under the inlet distortion condition can increase the worksum around the shock wave at the blade tip.

Figure 15 compares the time-averaged relative Mach number contours at 98% span. Figures 16(a) and 16(b) show the amplitudes and phase angles of the first pressure harmonic due to blade vibration on blade surfaces at 98% span. On the S.S., the amplitude of the first pressure harmonic, increases around

FIGURE 15. Comparison of the time-averaged relative Mach number contours at 98% span.

the shock wave, which aligns with the improved worksum in this region (see Fig. 12). On the P.S., the phase angle exhibits a sharp variation around the shock wave, which can further decrease the worksum and improve flutter stability. Although the phase angle changes from a positive to negative value around the flow-separation region on the P.S., it has minimal effect on worksum, as indicated by the streamwise distribution of worksum (referring to Fig. 14).

Besides the blade tip region, a significant discrepancy in the worksum is observed around 60% span. A detailed analysis will

(a) Amplitude

(b) Phase

FIGURE 16. Comparison of amplitude (a), and phase (b) for the first pressure harmonic at 98% span on blade surfaces.

be conducted to understand the mechanisms behind this phenomena. Figure 17 presents the streamwise distributions of the worksum at 60% span. Around the shock wave, the worksum is positive on the S.S., suggesting that the shock wave contributes to destabilizing the flutter system. As shown in Fig. 18, the strength of the shock wave is slightly enhanced on the S.S. (highlighted by dashed circles), leading to an increase in the worksum at the shock wave. Additionally, the worksum in the flow separation region (aft the shock wave referring to Fig. 18) on the S.S. is negative, indicating that flow separation has a stabilizing effect. As the shock wave intensity increases under the distorted inlet condition, the shock-boundary interaction improves. This, in turn,

increases the extent of flow separation and then enhances the effect of flow separation on worksum, leading to a smaller worksum aft the shock wave on the S.S. compared to the uniform inlet condition. In contrast to the S.S., the maximum worksum under the distorted inlet condition shifts forward and decreases compared to that under the uniform inlet condition. Aft the shock wave, the worksum transitions from negative to positive values, making the aeroelastic system more unstable under the distorted inlet condition. These results highlight the increase in worksum on the P.S. and decrease on the S.S. at 60% span, as shown in Fig. 13.

FIGURE 17. Comparison of worksum along the streamline at 60% span.

FIGURE 18. Comparison of the time-averaged relative Mach number contours at 60% span.

FIGURE 19. Comparison of the unsteady pressure contours under the uniform (a) and distorted inlet conditions (b) at 60% span

Figure 19 shows the unsteady pressure contours at 60% span. Figures 20(a) and 20(b) compare the time-averaged pressure, the amplitudes and phase angles of the first pressure harmonic on the S.S. and P.S., respectively. As shown in Fig. 19, the consideration of inlet distortion results in more pronounced unsteady pressure signals, thereby enhancing the non-linearity of the unsteady flow fields. As seen in Figs. 20(a) and 20(b), the time-averaged pressure under both uniform and distorted inlet conditions exhibits a slight discrepancy. This small difference leads to significant changes in the unsteady pressure signals due to blade vibrations. On the S.S., a visible difference in both amplitudes and phase angles of the first pressure harmonic can be observed before and around the shock wave. On the P.S., an obvious difference in the phase angles can only be observed. Therefore, it can be concluded that the changes in worksom on the P.S.

at 60% span are primarily due to variations in the phase angles of the unsteady pressure signals caused by blade vibrations.

(a) S.S.

(b) P.S.

FIGURE 20. Comparison of the time-averaged pressure, the first harmonic amplitude, and the phase angles on the S.S. (a), and the P.S. (b) at 60% span.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This work employs an efficient and robust Fourier-based numerical method, known as the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method, to investigate the effect of inlet distortion

on flutter stability. The numerical analysis reveals that the condition number of the discrete Fourier transform is approximately 2.00 for the ATDNHM, compared to 3.07 for the HB method. A smaller condition number indicates a more stable solution. Furthermore, the numerical results indicate that the inlet distortion can alter the sign of the log-dec at an IBPA of 0° , causing the aeroelastic system to become unstable at this IBPA. This is because the inlet distortion can enhance the non-linearity of the unsteady flow fields. The time-averaged flow fields, affected by the unsteady distorted disturbances, will change, which in turn leads to variations in aeroelastic performance. Under the distorted inlet condition, the strength of the shock wave is amplified, resulting in a more significant impact on flutter stability. On the S.S., the increased shock wave strength produces a more pronounced destabilizing effect on the aeroelastic system. Additionally, changes in shock wave strength can also influence the flow separation aft the shock wave. However, the flow separation at the middle span on the S.S. can stabilize the aeroelastic performance, leading to a more stable solution in this region. In conclusion, accounting for inlet distortion is crucial in flutter analysis, especially when fans/compressors operate under such conditions.

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